

Exploring and modeling cumulative bias and its asymmetry in student evaluations of teaching at a Polish university

Supplementary material

1. The SET questionnaire that was used for this paper.

Evaluation survey of the teaching staff of [university name]

Please, complete the following evaluation form, which aims to assess the lecturer's performance.

Only one answer should be indicated for each question. The answers are coded in the following way: 5- I strongly agree; 4- I agree; 3- Neutral; 2- I don't agree; 1- I strongly don't agree.

Questions	1	2	3	4	5
I learnt a lot during the course.	<input type="radio"/>				
I think that the knowledge acquired during the course is very useful.	<input type="radio"/>				
The professor used activities to make the class more engaging.	<input type="radio"/>				
If it was possible, I would enroll for the course conducted by this lecturer again.	<input type="radio"/>				
The classes started on time.	<input type="radio"/>				
The lecturer always used time efficiently.	<input type="radio"/>				
The lecturer delivered the class content in an understandable and efficient way.	<input type="radio"/>				
The lecturer was available when we had doubts.	<input type="radio"/>				
The lecturer treated all students equally regardless of their race, background and ethnicity.	<input type="radio"/>				

2. Summary statistics for variables used in regression models

Table A. Summary statistics for variables used in regression models.

	Minimum	Mean*	Maximum	Std. dev.
SET_score_avg	1	4.39	5	0.72
log_no_participants	1	4.43	7.91	0.94
resp_share	0.01	0.09	1	0.12
stud_grade_avg_cur	2.38	3.99	5	0.56
stud_grade_avg	2.38	3.96	5	0.54
percent_failed_cur	0	0.13	0.75	0.15
percent_failed	0	0.12	0.75	0.14
stud_grade_std_cur	0	0.80	1.77	
stud_grade_std	0	0.82	1.76	
class_duration	0	1.57	3	0.66
Monday	0	0.09	1	
Tuesday	0	0.13	1	
Wednesday	0	0.12	1	
Thursday	0	0.12	1	
Friday	0	0.08	1	
Saturday	0	0.29	1	
Sunday	0	0.17	1	
class_end_by_10	0	0.14	1	
class_end_10_14	0	0.41	1	
class_end_14_18	0	0.34	1	
class_end_18_22	0	0.11	1	
SET_score_1sem	1.22	4.40	5	0.43
prof	0	0.02	1	
dr	0	0.65	1	
ma	0	0.29	1	
no_dgr	0	0.04	1	
seniority (years)	1	5.50	11	3.21
male	0	0.54	1	
female	0	0.46	1	

Note: * The mean values for dummy {0,1} variables represent the percentage distribution across both categories. For instance, a value of 0.54 for the 'male' category indicates that 54% of faculty members are male.

Source: Authors own work

3. Estimation results of the OLS and quantile regressions, model 2cur.

The heatmap shows estimates of responses of the dependent variable to the independent variables. Estimated parameters that are insignificant at 0.1 level are represented by grey shading. The parameter estimate of the *percent_failed_cur* variable was divided by 2 to fit the heatmap scale.

Fig A. Estimation results of the OLS and quantile regressions, model 2cur, dependent variable *SET_score_avg*

Source: Authors own work.

4. Detailed methodology description

This study employs a comprehensive econometric approach to assess the cumulative biases in Student Evaluations of Teaching (SET). The methodology includes a combination of descriptive statistics, multivariate linear regression, and quantile regression models to estimate the impact of various biases on SET scores. The following subsections provide a detailed description of the research design, model specification, statistical methods employed to analyze the data, ethical considerations and limitations.

4.1. Research design

This study adopts a cross-sectional design using data from a single university in Poland during the 2020/2021 winter semester. The university, which offers courses in multiple disciplines and serves a diverse student population, transitioned to fully online teaching during the period of data collection due to the COVID-19 pandemic. This context provides an opportunity to examine how the shift to online teaching may have influenced SET ratings, particularly in terms of bias magnification.

The sample includes data for 1,021 course-teacher pairs, where each pair represents a specific course taught by an individual instructor. The unit of analysis is the course-instructor pair (identified by unique course and instructor IDs). The study focuses on several key independent variables that are known to influence SET results, including course difficulty, class size, instructor characteristics, and student demographics. These variables are operationalized based on the available dataset, as described in Section 2 of the main text.

4.2. Model specification

This study applies two primary statistical techniques to assess SET bias: multivariate linear regression and quantile regression. Both approaches allow for the estimation of the relationships between SET scores and various independent variables, while accounting for the fact that biases may operate differently across various levels of SET scores.

4.2.1 Multivariate linear regression

We estimate a set of linear regression models (Models 1 – 4 in the main text) to measure the relationship between SET scores and a range of independent variables. These models include both mean course grades and the percentage of students failing the course as proxies for course difficulty. To investigate the role of class size and other instructor/course characteristics, we include these factors as independent variables in the regression models. We also include previous SET scores (lagged by one semester) to examine the potential for halo effects, where prior performance may influence current evaluations.

4.2.2. Quantile regression

To examine the asymmetry of SET bias across different SET score levels (i.e., how biases affect low-rated versus high-rated courses differently), we apply quantile regression. This method allows for estimating the relationship between independent variables and the SET score at different points in the SET score distribution (e.g., the 10th, 50th, and 90th percentiles). This is crucial for understanding how biases might operate differently for courses that receive low, medium, or high ratings. Quantile regression provides a more nuanced understanding of SET bias, which traditional linear regression fails to capture.

The quantile regression model specification is similar to the linear regression model, but the dependent variable is the SET score at a specific quantile (e.g., 10th percentile, 50th percentile, or 90th percentile).

4.3. Statistical considerations

To ensure the validity of the regression results, several diagnostic tests were conducted:

- Multicollinearity: We assessed multicollinearity among the independent variables using a correlation heatmap.
- Heteroscedasticity: Given the presence of heteroscedasticity (non-constant variance of errors) in the SET data, robust standard errors were applied to correct for this issue.

- Model fit: The overall fit of the regression models was evaluated using Adjusted R-squared for the linear regressions, while the significance of the coefficients was assessed through t-tests and p-values.

4.4. Ethical considerations

The dataset used in this study was supplied by the university's administrative department. All data were anonymized to ensure the privacy of both students and instructors. As outlined in Section 2 of the main text, the dataset includes certain demographic characteristics of instructors and class sizes; however, because class subjects and other personal identifiers were coded, it is not possible to identify individual faculty members. The SET data itself does not contain any student information by design. The study was approved by the university's management, and no personally identifiable information was included in the analysis

4.5. Limitations of the methodology

- Generalizability: The data were collected from a single university, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other institutions or countries.
- Unobserved biases: Despite controlling for multiple known biases, there may still be unobserved variables influencing SET scores that cannot be captured in the models.